

EARTH SCIENCES

VITALITY STRUCTURE OF *SALIX ROSMARINIFOLIA* POPULATIONS IN FOREST AND MEADOW PHYTOCENOSSES

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Abstract

In the face of aggressive anthropogenic pressure on natural ecosystems, the urgent task of ecology is the study and preservation of rare species of flora. The paper presents studies of model populations of *Salix rosmarinifolia* L. in particular their vitality structure in forest and meadow phytocenoses of the Desniansko-Starohutsky National Nature Park and Roztochchya Biosphere Reserve. An analysis of the ecological and coenotic conditions of the species' existence showed that flat areas of land in deciduous and mixed forests, forest edges and meadows are quite favorable for the normal functioning of its populations. Vitality analysis showed that in Betuletum (pubescens)-salicetum (repentis) conditions on floodplain meadows and forest edges, thriving populations of *S. rosmarinifolia* were formed with quality indices of 0.46-0.49 and a predominance of plants of the middle vitality class (B). In the associations *Peucedano-pinetum*, *Salicetum (pentandro)-cinereae*, *Betuletum (humilis)-sphagnosum* equilibrium populations with quality indices of 0.26-0.34 were formed.

Keywords: *Salix rosmarinifolia* L., vitality analysis, population quality index, ontogeny, phytocenoses, rare species, biodiversity, association.

Introduction

The National Program for the Conservation of Biological Diversity for 2005-2025 [11] provides for monitoring and protection of populations of rare and endangered plant species. Species included in the nature conservation lists require special attention. This is due to the destruction of their biotopes and the reduction of their natural habitats. As a rule, rare species are represented by small populations, are characterized by low competitiveness and are confined to certain ecological niches [13].

In the period 2021-2023, field research was conducted on the territory of the Desniansko-Starohutsky National Park and Roztochchya Biosphere Reserve. Object of study - *Salix rosmarinifolia* - a regionally rare species that is protected in the Sumy regionis [10]. It is a deciduous, squat shrub up to 1 m tall. The species is widespread in Europe, Siberia, the northern regions of Central Asia, and the Far East [6]. It grows on moist soils - floodplain meadows, peat bogs, forest edges, forest glades, pine terraces both on plains and in mountainous areas [12].

Methods

In the process of conducting geobotanical observations, methods were used [1, 7, 9]. Population studies were conducted according to generally accepted methods [8].

To compare the impact of ecological and coenotic conditions on the development of populations of rare plant species, their vitality analysis was conducted, the theoretical foundations of which were formulated by Yu.A. Zlobin [14]. The assessment of the vitality of

populations was carried out on the basis of morphometric indicators of plants with the establishment of a quality index for each studied population.

Quantitative traits that reflect the vital state of plants in populations are selected taking into account the following criteria: they must be biologically significant for the species in different growth conditions, the set of traits includes those that, according to the results of factor analysis, have a valid confidence level. Traits that are highly correlated with each other are not used for analysis - for example, such pairs of traits as leaf length and its area. The integral morphoparameters that highlight the vitality of the population often include leaf surface area, plant height, number of generative organs, total phytomass of the plant or mass of inflorescences. But since the work investigated rare species, only those parameters were used, the collection of which does not cause damage to the plant.

There are 3 classes of vitality of individuals and populations: higher (A) within 0.66-1.0; average (B) within 0.33-0.66; lower (C) within 0-0.33.

The population quality index Q can vary from 0 to 0.5. Quality index values from 0 to 0.17 indicate that the population is depressed; if Q is within 0.18-0.34, the population is in equilibrium; Q values from 0.35 to 0.5 indicate that the population is thriving.

In the process of collecting morphometric data, due to the rarity of the studied species, exclusively non-destructive methods were used [3, 5]. This methods involve the use of only those morphometric parameters in the analysis of populations that can be measured without harm to plants, which is provided for by the provisions of the Convention on Biological Diversity and the

Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Flora and Fauna [2].

For the convenience of statistical processing of actual data and graphical presentation of results, the Statistics for Windows, Excel, Vital application packages were used.

Results

Salix rosmarinifolia occurs in several habitats in the park, in floodplain meadows, peat bogs, and in depressions near water bodies. The area of population fields of *S. rosmarinifolia* varies depending on the ecological and coenotic conditions of existence within 50 - 400 m².

Fig. 1. Locations of *Salix rosmarinifolia* populations in the Desniansko-Starohutsky National Nature Park [4]

The second population (P2) is located in square 53 on section 5 of the Starohutsky forest massif in the Peucedano-pinetum group. The canopy cover of the tree stand is 80%, the shrub layer cover is 45%, the projective cover of the herbaceous-shrub layer is 45%, and the moss layer is 80%. The area of the population field is 40 m². The tree layer is dominated by *Pinus Sylvestris* (80%) and *Betula pendula* (10%), while the shrub layer is dominated by *Corylus avellana*, *Frangula alnus* with a projective cover of 30%, *Salix cinerea*, and *Sorbus aucuparia*. The herbaceous-shrub layer is dominated by *Vaccinium myrtillus* with a projective cover of 50%, *Molinia caerulea*, *Trientalis europaea*, *Rubus saxatilis*, and *Festuca ovina*. The moss layer is represented by the species *Dicranum polysetum*, *Pleurozium schreberi*. The population density of *S. rosmarinifolia* is 0.25 pcs./10 m².

The third population (P3) of *S. rosmarinifolia* is located in the area 111 of the Starohutsky forest massif in the ass. *Salicetum pentandro – cinereae*. The canopy cover of the tree stand is 20%, shrubs – 80%. The projective cover of the herbaceous and shrub layer is 60%, moss layer – 40%. The dominant species of the tree layer: *Alnus glutinosa*, *Betula pendula*, shrub layer - *Salix cinerea*, *Frangula alnus*, herbaceous and shrub layer - *Carex elongata*, *Caltha palustris*, *Thelypteris palustris*, *Filipendula ulmaria*, *Gallium palustre*, *Potentilla palustris*, *Phragmites australis*. The moss layer

The first population (P1) is located in the floodplain of the Desna River south of the village of Borovichi (Fig. 1) in the ass. *Betuleto (pubescens)-salicetum (repentis)*. The dominant species are *Frangula alnus*, *Salix rosmarinifolia*, *S. cinerea*, *Deschampsia cespitosa*, *Lysimachia vulgaris*, *Potentilla erecta*. The projective cover of the herbaceous-shrub layer is 70%, the moss layer is absent. The area of the population field of the willow is 50 m², the population density is 3 pcs./10 m².

is represented by *Climacium dendroides*, *Aulacomnium palustre*, *Calliergonella cuspidata*. The area of the population field is 100 m², population density - 1 pc./10 m².

The fourth population (P4) of *S. rosmarinifolia*, which was studied, is located in the area 31 of the Starohutsky forest massif in the ass. *Betulo-Salicetum repentis*. The canopy cover of the tree stand is 20%, the canopy cover of the shrubs is 60%. The projective cover of the herbaceous-shrub layer is 55%, the moss layer is 45%. The dominant tree layer is *P. Sylvestris* (20%), the shrub layer is *S. rosmarinifolia* (50%), *S. cinerea* (10%), including the undergrowth of *P. sylvestris*, *B. pubescens*. The herbaceous-shrub layer is dominated by *Calamagrostis canescens*, *Geum rivale*, *Filipendula ulmaria*, *Lysimachia vulgaris*, *Phragmites australis*, *Potentilla palustris*, *Agrostis stolonifera*, *Carex juncella*, *C. rostrata*, *Equisetum palustre*. The moss layer is dominated by *Aulacomnium palustre* and *Climacium dendroides*. The area of the population field of the willow is 50 m², the population density is 5 pcs./10 m².

For comparison, the fifth population (P5) of *S. rosmarinifolia* was examined in more humid conditions on the territory of the Roztochchya biosphere reserve, namely to the northeast of the village of Zhornyska, Yavoriv district, Lviv region. The landscape is a reclamation site on a peat bog. The population is located in the

Betuletum (humilis)-sphagnosum on an area of about 100 m². The woody layer is absent in places, and in some areas it reaches 40%, *B. pubescens* prevails. The shrub layer is dominated by *Frangula alnus*, *Betula humilis*, *S. rosmarinifolia*. The herbaceous-shrub layer is dominated by *Molinia caerulea*, *Deshampsia caespitosa*, *Gallium boreale*, *Festuca ovina*. The moss

layer is dominated by *Brachytecium campestris*, *Dicranum bonjeani*, *Plagimonium ellipticum*. Population density of *S. rosmarinifolia* – 4 pcs./10m².

During the study, metric and allometric morphological parameters of *S. rosmarinifolia* plants were determined using non-destructive methods (Table 1).

Table 1

Confidence levels of morphometric data *S. rosmarinifolia*

Dependnt Variable	Test of SS Whole Model vs. SS Residual (+ Salix Marukhat1.sta)										
	Multiple R	Multiple R?	Adjusted R?	SS Model	df Model	MS Model	SS Residual	df Residual	MS Residual	F	p
H Salix	0,640549	0,410303	0,396178	29973	4	7493	4,307768E+04	167	258	29,04906	0,000000
IL Salix	0,823824	0,678687	0,670990	49	4	12	2,333752E+01	167	0	88,18541	0,000000
SL Salix	0,647996	0,419899	0,406004	0	4	0	3,114586E-01	167	0	30,22203	0,000000
AL Salix	0,826126	0,682483	0,674878	34	4	8	1,578913E+01	167	0	89,73921	0,000000
A-Salix	0,393931	0,155181	0,134946	186428009	4	46607002	1,014927E+09	167	6077409	7,66889	0,000011
NI- Salix	0,240518	0,057849	0,035283	5126022	4	1281506	8,348420E+07	167	499905	2,56350	0,040249
D - Salix	0,471090	0,221926	0,203290	7	4	2	2,529767E+01	167	0	11,90815	0,000000
Dk - Salix	0,168275	0,028316	0,005042	2	4	1	7,810371E+01	167	0	1,21666	0,305660
Pr-Salix	0,618904	0,383042	0,368264	1376	4	344	2,215913E+03	167	13	25,92070	0,000000
B1-Salix	0,358997	0,128879	0,108013	1341	4	335	9,066850E+03	167	54	6,17672	0,000117
Ng - Salix	0,453947	0,206068	0,187052	1186410	4	296603	4,570959E+06	167	27371	10,83637	0,000000
H/Ng Salix	0,147495	0,021755	-0,001676	0	4	0	4,270105E+00	167	0	0,92846	0,448848
H/A Salix	0,176823	0,031266	0,008063	0	4	0	4,720039E-03	167	0	1,34750	0,254487
NL/Ng Salix	0,333830	0,111443	0,090160	418	4	104	3,329484E+03	167	20	5,23628	0,000535
RE1- Ng/A *100 Salix	0,275202	0,075736	0,053598	86	4	22	1,053411E+03	167	6	3,42107	0,010203

To determine the quality of *S. rosmarinifolia* populations, such parameters as plant height, leaf surface area and number of inflorescences were used. These parameters had a sufficient coefficient of variation in different ecological-cenotic conditions. (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The value of key morphometric parameters of *S. rosmarinifolia* in different ecological and coenotic conditions

Fig. 3. Histogram of the frequency distribution of vitality classes of *S. rosmarinifolia* in the total sample

The histogram of the frequency distribution of vitality classes of *S. rosmarinifolia* shows that the main group of plants in the population is made up of individuals of the middle vitality class (Fig. 3).

Table 2

Vitality structure of *Salix rosmarinifolia* populations in different ecological and coenotic conditions

Phytocoenotic conditions	Vitality classes			Quality index Q	Population type	Location
	A	B	C			
<i>Betuleto (pubescens)-salicetum (repentis)</i>	0,27	0,71	0,02	0,49	Prosperous	Desna River floodplain
<i>Peucedano -pinetum</i>	0,0	0,62	0,38	0,31	Equilibrium	Square 53
<i>Salicetum (pentandro)-cinereae</i>	0,0	0,69	0,31	0,34	Equilibrium	Square 111
<i>Betuleto (pubescens)-salicetum (repentis)</i>	0,24	0,68	0,08	0,46	Prosperous	Square 31
<i>Betuletum (humilis)- sphagnosum</i>	0,0	0,51	0,49	0,26	Equilibrium	“Roztocha”

According to the ratio of vitality classes, two populations of *S. rosmarinifolia* were found to be thriving, both in *Betuleto (pubescens)-salicetum (repentis)* conditions (Table 2). The highest quality index of 0.49 was in the population that formed in the floodplain of the Desna River southwest of the village of Borovichi on an area of 50 m². The quality index of 0.46 was in the

population that formed in the area of 5 m² in the area of 31 of the Starogut forest massif. The remaining populations are in equilibrium with different quality indices: Q 0.34 was in the conditions of *Salicetum (pentandro)-cinereae* in the area of 111 SLM, Q 0.31 - in the population of *S. rosmarinifolia* in the area of 5 m². 53 SLM in the *Peucedano - pinetum* association with an area of

40 m², Q 0.26 - in the population under *Betuletum* (*humilis*)-*sphagnosum* conditions on an area of 100 m² on the territory of the Roztochchya biosphere reserve, namely to the northeast of the village of Zhornyska, Yavoriv district, Lviv region, on a reclaimed peatland.

Anthropogenic impact on populations of rare plants in the park is constant, but during the years of military aggression from the east, the main factor in

such impact was forest fires, which became more frequent as a result of regular bombing of the border area.

During the long-term fires in 2023, according to observations by the Global Fire Information Management System, 2,529.2 hectares of the Starogutsky forest massif in the eastern part were affected, which is 15.6% of the park's territory (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. The territory of the Desniansko-Starohutskyi National Park during the fire in May 2023 according to the Global Fire Information Management System

An extensive ground fire that broke out in the rainless spring of 2023 due to the use of heavy firearms and probable arson significantly affected the populations of the grass-shrub layer in the eastern part of the Starogutsky forest massif. Populations of local species such as *Pinus sylvestris*, *Ulmus glabra*, *Acer campestre*, *A. platanooides*, *Primula veris*, *Corydalis solida*, *Clinopodium vulgare*, *Gallium boreale*, *Cardamine bulbifera*, *Steris viscaria*, *Pimpinella saxifrage*, *Trifolium montanum*, *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*, *V. myrtillus*, *Filipendula vulgaris* were affected to varying degrees.

Due to the effects of high temperatures, populations of rare flora species listed in the Red Book of Ukraine have suffered: *Huperzia selago*, *Diphasiastrum zelleri*, *Lycopodium annotinum*, *Epipactis helleborine*, *Dactylorhiza incarnata*, *D. fuchsia*, *Platanthera bifolia*, *Carex brunnescens*, *Salix starkeana*, *S. rosmarinifolia*. The final determination of the state of their populations will be possible only after the end of hostilities. The probability of their underground diaspores remaining in moist areas of soil in relief depressions where the fire did not reach.

Conclusions and suggestions

Vitality analysis is an important tool for comparative analysis of the viability of plant populations in certain ecological and coenotic conditions. But to protect populations of rare species, including *S. rosmarinifolia*, it is necessary to overcome the consequences of military aggression on the territory of the Desniansko-Starohutskyi National Park.

To restore disturbed forest and meadow ecosystems and revive populations of rare flora species on the territory of the National Park of Forests and Forests, it is necessary to:

- After the end of hostilities, carry out measures to demine the territory, clear the soil of military artifacts, and level deep craters with the involvement of military specialists.
- Monitor the state of the park's vegetation cover to assess the current state of the park's forest and meadow ecosystems. Carefully investigate the areas that have been significantly affected by explosions and fires. Based on the monitoring results, develop strategic programs for the restoration of disturbed phytocenoses; organize groups of volunteers for the artificial restoration of damaged perennial plantings and undergrowth to feed phytophagous plants.
- Forest reclamation works. In the process of restoring damaged forest ecosystems, it is necessary to pay attention to the undergrowth, namely to plants that provide food and shelter for wild birds.
- To protect and preserve rare species of flora in the park, it is necessary to review and improve the legislative framework in the field of environmental protection and nature management in the recreational and economic functional zones of national natural parks.
- Continue the formation of an ecological network that will connect all natural zones of Ukraine with ecological corridors. This process is one of the most effective ways to preserve biological diversity. The sustainable functioning of the ecological network is ensured by introducing special regimes of economic activity and regulations for the use of natural resources within the territories of ecological corridors, which can be achieved by establishing a special nature protection status for such territories.

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